

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Los Angeles
Kaiser Permanente School of Anesthesia

IMPLEMENTATION OF AN EARLY ACTIVE PROGRESSIVE MOBILITY PROTOCOL IN
THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Helene Margarite Mendez

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Ayman Tailakh, PhD, RN, Team Leader
Dr. Raymund Gantioque DNP, RNFA, ACNP-BC, Team Member

May 2024

Author Note

Helene Mendez - <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6498-4440>

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.13737669

© 2024 Helene Mendez

ABSTRACT

Research shows that implementing a mobility protocol in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) reduces the incidence of ICU - acquired weakness, shortens hospital stays, increases patient mobility, and improves patient outcomes. This study is a quality improvement project investigating the impact of implementing an early progressive mobility protocol in an Intensive Care Unit in Southern California. The aims of this quality improvement project were to reduce the incidence of ICU-acquired weakness by decreasing ICU length of stay and improving patient mobility. ACE STAR Model of Knowledge Transformation was the framework used to guide the implementation of the new protocol. An Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale and nurse demographics survey, was administered pre- and post-intervention to assess the nurse's attitudes toward adopting a new protocol and collect nurse demographics. All ICU nurses were educated on the new early progressive mobility protocol. The nurses were instructed to provide each patient with early progressive mobility each shift and document the mobility level in the electronic medical record. Intensive Care Unit length of stay and Bedside Mobility Assessment Tool scores were compared pre-and post-intervention and there was no statistically significant improvement. Post-survey, however, did find that 59% of nurses saw improvement in patient overall well-being after early progressive mobility implementation. Although there was not statistically significant improvement in this project with continued training and implementation there is room for improvement.

Keywords: immobility, intensive care unit, ICU, ICU-AW, EPM, early progressive mobility, ACE STAR Model of Knowledge Transformation, Evidence Based Practice Attitude Scale, EBPAS, length of stay, LOS, Bedside Mobility Assessment Tool, BMAT,

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vi
BACKGROUND	1
Problem Statement.....	2
Purpose Statement.....	3
Project Objectives.....	3
Supporting Framework	3
Framework Discussion.....	4
Integration of the STAR Model	5
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	8
ICU-AW.....	8
Early Progressive Mobility Tools	10
Facilitators and Barriers to EPM.....	11
Strategies to Implement EPM.....	12
Summary.....	14
METHODS	15
Project Design.....	15
Setting	16
Participants.....	16
Ethical Considerations	16
Procedures.....	16
RESULTS	21
Participant Demographics.....	21
Pre and Post EBPAS© Survey.....	21
Pre- and Post ICU LOS and BMAT Scores.....	22
DISCUSSION.....	23
Limitations	24

Recommendations.....	25
Conclusion	26
REFERENCES	27
APPENDIX A: Figure 1: Stevens STAR Model of Knowledge	31
APPENDIX B: Figure 2: AACN’s Early Progressive Mobility Protocol	32
APPENDIX C: IRB Letter of Exemption.....	33
APPENDIX D: Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Project Summary	34
APPENDIX E: Letter of Support.....	35
APPENDIX F: Demographic Survey	36
APPENDIX G: Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale (EBPAS ©).....	37
APPENDIX H: Table 1: Descriptive Statistics.....	38
APPENDIX J EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages	40
Figure 3: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages	40
Figure 4: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Subscale 1: Requirements.....	41
Figure 5: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Subscale 2: Appeal	42
Figure 6: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Subscale 3: Openness	43
Figure 7: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Subscale 4: Divergence	44
APPENDIX I: ICU LOS and BMAT Scores.....	45
Figure 8: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages	45
Figure 9: EBPAS© Pre and Post Mean Averages, Subscale 1: Requirements.....	46

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The completion of my Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) would not have been possible without the love and support from those around me. Thank you to my parents, Martha, and Joe, who instilled in me the importance of education and for their continued support and encouragement throughout my educational journey. To my late Grandmother Esperanza, you're my motivation, thank you for teaching me that education is important because it is not only something no one can ever take away, but it is also something you can share without losing.

Thank you to all of my family and friends who have cheered me on along the way. To Mirella and Vero, gracias for always reminding me to "¡Échale ganas!" To Santos, thank you for always being so supportive and encouraging, you're a blessing in my life. To Vanessa and Kirsten, you ladies have been so helpful, and your feedback has been vital in the success of my project, I can't wait to put more of our ideas into action. To my DNP friends, Christa, and Dana, thank you ladies for all your support. To my beastie, Tia Lene loves you always and forever.

Thank you to my SFMC family, I would not be where I am today without the opportunity I was given as a new graduate RN. SFMC will forever be my home. Thank you to all of the SFMC ICU staff for your hard work. To all my seasoned ICU nurses, you have watched me grow from a baby nurse to where I am today, thank you for teaching me everything I know about ICU. To Dr. Meher Tabatabai for always believing in me and being a great mentor and friend, you're more valuable than you know. Thank you Dr. Arunpal Sehgal for being supportive and taking the time to teach me. A special thank you to Dr. Payrus Patel and Dr. Anna Carchi for your continued support and encouragement, I am thankful for all you do.

Background

Immobility is a significant problem in the intensive care unit (ICU) because "bedrest" for "safety" is a long-standing accepted practice in the care of ICU patients (Amundadottir et al., 2021). Nurses are found to be reluctant to mobilize ICU patients due to various reasons, including weakness, extent of critical illness, and increased risk for falls (Dirkes & Kozlowski, 2019). However, the hazard of immobility in critically ill patients far outweighs its risks. Immobilization of a critically ill patient causes a fast functional decline creating a cascade of problems such as delirium, venous stasis leading to thrombosis, and an increased cardiac workload leading to decreased cardiac output among many other complications (Tirona, 2023). Intensive Care Unit-Acquired Weakness (ICU-AW) is a term used to describe a neuromuscular complication causing critical illness associated polyneuropathy and polymyopathy induced by prolonged immobilization (Escalon et al., 2020).

Research has found that ICU-AW occurs in 46% of critically ill patients who have a prolonged stay in the ICU (Escalon et al., 2020). The global occurrence of ICU-AW is about 25% to 31% (Zhou et al., 2022). Patients with ICU-AW are more likely to have a longer length of stay (LOS) in the hospital, increased hospital costs, difficulty weaning from mechanical ventilation (MV), and an increased mortality rate (Sarfati et al., 2018). The recovery time from ICU-AW can take weeks or even months, and some patients never regain their full pre-hospital functional capacity (Zhou et al., 2022). About 84% to 95% of patients who survive ICU-AW are found to have a poor quality of life (QOL), prolonged impaired immobility, and an increased mortality rate for up to five years post-discharge (Escalon et al., 2020). Prevention of ICU-AW is essential because it directly affects the QOL of a patient post-discharge (Alamri et al., 2019).

Problem Statement

The incidence of ICU-AW is found to be increased in critically ill patients in the ICU, who have risk factors such as a severe infection, sepsis, multiple organ failure, uncontrolled hyperglycemia and/or have been treated with certain medications like corticosteroids or neuromuscular blocking agents (Sarfati et al., 2018). However, despite numerous risk factors, research has also shown that severity of illness does not directly impact the strength of a patient (Escalon et al., 2020). Mobility in critically ill patients is the only modifiable risk factor found in preventing ICU-AW, and it is directly associated with progressive muscle loss, contributing to severe muscle weakness (Escalon et al., 2020). Each week, an immobilized critically ill patient suffers a reduction in muscle strength of about 40% overall (Tirona, 2023) and loses about 14% of muscle mass per week (Escalon et al., 2020).

In order to reduce the incidence of ICU-AW and improve strength in patients who are admitted to the ICU, a protocol must be in place to encourage early progressive mobility (EPM). One study showed that after implementing EPM, the percentage of patients who were able to walk independently at discharge increased from 25% to 50% (Dirkes & Kozlowski, 2019). Research also indicates that EPM not only improves the physical condition of a patient, but it also improves cognitive and psychological health (Bach & Hetland, 2022). In critically ill patients, EPM decreases the need for sedation; thus, reducing the incidence of ICU delirium (Schallom et al., 2020). Implementation of EPM using a safety screening tool and protocol that offers both in-bed and out-of-bed progressive mobility has been proven to be safe and feasible to use in critically ill patients (Sarfati et al., 2018). The use of an EPM tool in the ICU is proven to reduce ICU-AW, length of ICU stays, time of MV, and mortality (Escalon et al., 2020). In

addition, early and appropriate application of an EPM tool improves functional status at discharge and improves overall patient outcomes (Bach & Hetland, 2022).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to implement an EPM screening tool and protocol in the ICU as part of the mobility component of the ICU Liberation ABCDEF bundle in order to improve patient mobility and reduce the incidence of ICU-AW. The specific aims of this project were to 1) conduct a pre- and post-test to assess nursing attitudes towards implementing EPM, 2) educate the nursing staff in the ICU regarding the hazards of immobility and implement the EPM tool and protocol for patients in the ICU, 3) measure the effectiveness of the EPM tool by comparing the Bedside Mobility Assessment Tool (BMAT) score and ICU LOS score 30 days pre- and post-implementation.

Project Objectives

The objectives of this doctoral project were to:

- Conduct a pre- and post-test to assess nursing attitudes towards implementing EPM.
- Educate the nursing staff in the ICU regarding the hazards of immobility.
- Implement the EPM tool and protocol for patients in the ICU.
- Measure the effectiveness of the EPM tool by comparing the ICU LOS and BMAT score 30 days pre- and post-implementation.

Supporting Framework

A theoretical framework is a theory used to help the reader understand and investigate an identified problem (Walden, 2023). Theoretical frameworks can be used in both qualitative and quantitative studies (Walden, 2023). The ACE STAR Model of Knowledge Transformation, also known as the STAR model, is a theoretical framework centered on evidence-based practice

(EBP) (Stevens, 2022). The STAR model was created in 2004 by Dr. Kathleen Stevens in conjunction with the University of Texas Health Science Center in San Antonio (Stevens, 2022). The STAR model encompasses both nursing science and EBP to provide the nursing profession with a method to examine the process, roles, and research methods for evaluating an intervention of practice change (Stevens, 2022). It focuses on using clinical based decision-making strategies to investigate health problems in order to determine the most effective interventions to address it (Stevens, 2022). The STAR model utilizes EBPs by incorporating research, clinical expertise, and the patient's preferences (Stevens, 2013).

Framework Discussion

The five-point STAR model illustrates the five major stages of knowledge transformation within the framework (Stevens, 2022). The stages of knowledge transformation are meant to reduce the time and volume of research and literature gathered by providing information that is comprehensive and based on systematic reviews. The goal is to be able to directly apply the information to the clinical setting (Stevens, 2013). The five stages are: 1. Discovery Research, 2. Evidence Summary, 3. Translation to Guidelines, 4. Practice Integration, and 5. Process, Outcome Evaluation (Stevens, 2022; Figure 1 in Appendix A).

The STAR model is relevant to the nursing field because it's an efficient approach to applying EBPs into nursing care by allowing the nursing professional to have access to a summary of research available on a topic rather than spend time deciphering through multiple studies (Stevens, 2013). This framework promotes the use of EBPs by making it easy for the nurse professional to use research-based information to improve practice (Nursing Bird, 2022). It also assists in identifying barriers to success that often occur when attempting to implement

research into practice while providing EBP solutions to the barriers (Nursing Bird, 2022).

Practice changes are research-based when applying the STAR model (Nursing Bird, 2022).

The STAR model has been used successfully in various settings through the implementation of EBP interventions to make improvements within the healthcare field. This model has been used to successfully improve outcomes in adult renal transplant patients by addressing medication adherence by implementing a specialized acute care education bundle for nursing staff. The implementation led to decreased readmission rates, decreased (LOS), and lowered hospital costs (Garcia, 2020). It has also been used successfully in the educational setting to develop and implement an education strategy, which increased the passing rate of the NCLEX for students in a Baccalaureate Nursing Program (Bonis et al., 2007).

Previous process improvement projects in the clinical setting have shown the STAR model to be the best choice when selecting a successful EBP framework. Thus, the STAR model has been selected for the current DNP project as it is the most appropriate choice for implementing an EPM protocol in the ICU to improve patient mobility, decrease ICU LOS, and reduce ICU-AW incidences. The project was implemented by integrating the STAR model's five stages of knowledge transformation.

Integration of the STAR Model

The integration of the STAR model was with the first stage of conducting a review of literature (ROL) to discover new knowledge about how to reduce ICU-AW incidences. In the present project, the ROL consisted of searching for research regarding prevention measures for ICU-AW, tools, and protocols for early mobility (EM), EPM, barriers and facilitators to EPM, and strategies to implement EPM. The second stage involved using the knowledge gathered through the ROL and synthesizing the gathered research to identify similarities and differences

in the literature. The strongest evidence was then identified. In the third stage, guidelines were developed using the synthesized EBPs. There was not an existing EPM in the present facility. The PL used an EPM guideline developed by the American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN) to develop a specific guideline tailored to the facility to implement the protocol in the ICU (AACN, 2013; Appendix B, Figure 2). The fourth stage of this project was the application of the guidelines into practice. This step identified the key stakeholders who were needed to ensure implementation of the EPM protocol. The key stakeholders included the ICU director, the ICU Medical Director, ICU Intensivists, ICU Nursing Supervisor, and ICU nurses. A meeting was held with the key stakeholders to go over the proposed EPM protocol and it was unanimously agreed upon to implement the protocol into the ICU workflow. To facilitate education and implementation of the new protocol, a poster board with the protocol guidelines was created as a visual to optimize education, badge buddies with the EPM protocol were created and distributed to all ICU nurses, and every 2-hour turning schedule with assigned turning buddies was implemented in the ICU. The education of ICU nurses took place over the course of a seven day period during day and night huddles to target all ICU nurses. Nurses who were not present during the week of education received one-to-one education by the PL. An anonymous demographic and attitude survey was also distributed via Qualtrics© to the ICU nurses both pre- and post-implementation of the EPM protocol. The final stage was the evaluation of the new EPM protocol and its effect on the incidence of ICU-AW by measuring the average ICU LOS and average BMAT scores 30 days pre- and post-implementation. De-identified data for average ICU LOS and average BMAT scores 30 days pre- and post-implementation of the EPM protocol were provided to the PL by the electronic medical record (EMR) analysts via secured report.

Demographic data and attitudes survey responses were collected from Qualtrics© and evaluated by the PL.

Review of Literature

Reviews of the Literature are an essential component of the evidence-based practice process because they ensure that high-quality evidence is reviewed and duplication of research is avoided (Maggio et al., 2016). An adequate ROL will assist other researchers in seeing how the evidence was found, in what context, and the methodology that was used to produce the same results (Maggio et al., 2016). A literature review was conducted to examine the implementation of EPM protocols in the ICU setting. The focus of this project was on implementing a protocol for EPM in the ICU. However, it is also essential to review studies involving the impact of the implementation of the entire ABCDEF bundle and the impact of ICU-AW to have a comprehensive understanding of the need to implement an EPM tool. The databases used in this literature review were CINAHL and PubMed. These databases were searched using the terms “early mobility”, “ABCDEF”, “ICU-AW”, “ICU acquired weakness”, and “early mobilization”.

The review of literature was limited to peer-reviewed journal articles written in English involving only adults that were published between 2018 to 2023. Articles were selected if they focused on implementing an EM protocol in the adult ICU. Inclusion criteria were randomized control trials, quasi-experimental designs, systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and quality improvement projects. Articles were excluded if they focused on delirium or COVID-19, all pilot studies, and any study that focused on staff perceptions of EM. A total of 12 articles were selected for this review to evaluate the implementation of an EM protocol in the ICU.

ICU-AW

ICU-AW is a severe complication causing polyneuropathy and myopathy that occurs in about 25-31% of critically ill patients globally (Zhou et al., 2022). Studies have shown that a healthy person on bed rest can lose about 5% of muscle mass in a seven day period; in contrast, a

person who is critically ill can lose up to 16 % of muscle mass in the same seven day period (Escalon et al., 2020). According to Escalon et al. (2020), ICU-AW incidence can climb up to 46% in patients who have had a prolonged ICU stay. The consequences of ICU-AW have been shown to be life-limiting and can cause a range of problems from limb and respiratory weakness to prolonged MV, which leads to extended ICU LOS, increasing healthcare costs, and eventually mortality (Zhou et al., 2022).

Escalon et al. (2020) found that the effects of ICU-AW do not end at discharge, patients recently discharged from the ICU suffered muscle wasting and joint weakness attributed to ICU-AW for up to 2 years post-discharge from the hospital. About half of the same patients in Escalon et al.'s (2020) study was also found to be unable to return to work for one year after hospital discharge. Further research by Escalon et al. (2020) found that 84-95% of patients who developed ICU-AW continue to have impaired mobility symptoms and a lower QOL for up to 5 years post-discharge. There is currently no definite cause of ICU-AW or definitive treatment; however, research has found that mobility is the only modifiable risk factor (Escalon et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2022).

In Escalon et al.'s (2020) study, an EM protocol was implemented in an ICU and resulted in a statistically significant reduction in LOS ($t [538] = 2.01; p < 0.05$). Additionally, ICU-AW was also reduced as a result of early mobilization and reduction of LOS overall. Likewise, Zhou et al. (2022) also implemented an EM protocol in the ICU but also implemented an EM protocol with the addition of a nutrition regimen (EMN). Zhou et al. (2022) results were statistically significant in decreasing ICU-AW for both the EM group (2%, 95% CI 0.1–10.6%) and the EMN group (2%, 95% CI 0.1–10.6%) in comparison to the control group (16%, 95% CI 7.2-

29.1%); therefore, nutrition did not affect ICU-AW as both intervention groups were at 2%. This indicates that EM alone reduced ICU-AW seven times less than the control group.

Early Progressive Mobility Tools

Immobility is one of the most significant indicators of poor outcomes for hospitalized patients. It is essential to implement EM protocols in the ICU to improve patient outcomes. Substantial research indicates that EM reduces the physical decline that occurs in hospitalized patients (Turner et al., 2020). The first way to implement EM in hospitalized patients is with a nurse-driven tool, such as the one used in the study by Turner et al. (2020), the BMAT. The BMAT gauges the patient's functional status and then allows the nurse to mobilize the patient safely based on their current functional status. Falkenstein et al. (2020) developed an EM protocol with mobilization criteria to improve mobility in patients in a trauma ICU. The mobility program implemented by Falkenstein et al. (2020) was found to be safe, reduced LOS, decreased time of MV, and reduced hospital costs.

Alamri et al. (2019) also found that implementing an EM protocol improved outcomes in their population of stroke patients and recommended that EPM protocols be implemented as a standard of care in the ICU. Bach and Hetland (2022) found that nurse-driven intervention protocols regardless of the type are essential in ensuring that EPM occurs because it allows the nurse to incorporate it into their workflow. EM is a key component in improving patient outcomes. The use of the BMAT has been established by many facilities and is the standard mobility assessment tool endorsed by the American Nurses Association (Boynton et al., 2020). In the present project, the BMAT has been adopted as the primary tool for determining the safety of EPM for patients across all care continuums.

Facilitators and Barriers to EPM

To be successful in the implementation of a new protocol into a high-acuity unit such as the ICU, it is essential to identify facilitators for implementation. Zhou et al. (2022) mention that the department directors must be very supportive of implementing EM in the units; thus, all nurses and ICU intensivists actively participate in implementing the EM protocol despite time constraints with a busy workflow. Dirkes & Kozlowski (2019) and Schallom et al. (2020) found that a major facilitator to implementing a new EM protocol was also adhering to the ABCDEF bundle as it encompasses mobility as a strategy to prevent ICU-AW. Schallom et al. (2020) found that for an EM protocol to be successfully implemented, it is crucial to use the interdisciplinary approach. The use of a physical therapist (PT) to help implement the EM protocol with nursing staff was essential to the success of the implementation and was also found to promote collaboration within the ICU (Schallom et al., 2020).

There are multiple factors that act as barriers to the implementation of EM protocols in the ICU setting. Barriers include inadequate staffing and equipment, costs, perceived time constraints by nursing staff, and hesitation regarding patient safety would cause delays in implementing EM in critical care settings (Dirkes & Kozlowski, 2019; Escalon et al., 2020). Oversedation is also a considerable barrier to implementing EM in the ICU (Escalon et al., 2020). Escalon et al. (2020) created an as-needed sedation protocol to combat the oversedation barrier, preventing continuous sedation and allowing sedation breaks to coincide with EM sessions.

In contrast, Bach and Hetland (2022) and Tirona (2023) found that the top barriers to the implementation of EM in the ICU were time constraints, inadequate staffing, lack of knowledge regarding the benefits of mobility, and hemodynamic instability of ICU patients. To combat

these perceived barriers, the EM implementation focused on the nursing role (Bach & Hetland, 2022; Tirona, 2023). The interventions were created to be nurse-led and both research teams developed screening tools to ensure the safety of mobilization of the critically ill patient as well as education of nursing and ancillary staff on the safety and positive outcomes associated with EM in the critically ill patient (Bach & Hetland, 2022; Tirona, 2023).

Other studies found that barriers to implementation of EM in the ICU were mainly related to safety (Dirkes & Kozlowski, 2019; Zhou et al., 2022). The biggest cause for concern about implementing the EM protocol in Zhou et al.'s (2022) study was attributed to the critically ill patient's safety regarding the stability of lines, tubes, and drains and the risk of dislodgement of these items. Dirkes & Kozlowski (2019) also found that nursing staff were very concerned that ICU patients were too ill to be mobilized. The second aspect of safety-related concerns was nursing concerns for adverse events that could occur with EM (Zhou et al., 2022). Through education and evidence of the success of EM in other patients, Zhou et al. (2022) was able to increase confidence within the nursing staff and assure the nursing staff to implement the EM protocol by educating and training nurses.

Strategies to Implement EPM

Implementing any new protocol into the health care system can be difficult. Implementing an EM protocol into the daily workflow of a busy unit such as the ICU faces many challenges (Dubb et al., 2016). Dubb et al. (2016) reviewed 40 studies that evaluated strategies for EM among ICU patients and found that 50% of the studies reviewed that used an interdisciplinary team approach were the most effective in implementing EM, 45% of the studies used a combination of strategies for EM, and 17% established inclusion/exclusion criteria for EM. Nurse-driven interventions such as screening tools that ensure the safety of mobilization of

critically ill patients can be created to implement protocols while also including the essential stakeholders such as nurses (Bach & Hetland, 2022; Tirona, 2023). Literature provided developed inclusion and exclusion criteria for patients who are suitable for EM in addition to using a protocol to follow for EM (Amundadottir et al., 2021; Sarfati et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2022). The criteria for the safety of EM initiation and an EM protocol were developed using an interdisciplinary approach. Tirona (2020) also used an incentive-based approach where the staff was given lunch on the first day of implementation, treats and badge buddies with the EM protocol were handed out, and Mobility champions were appointed on a shift-to-shift basis.

Dubb et al. (2016) found that ICU culture was also reported as a barrier in 60% of the studies reviewed, with 30% being attributed to a lack of knowledge regarding mobility. Adequate education of nursing and ancillary staff on the safety and positive outcomes associated with EM in critically ill patients was also found to be an impactful strategy for successful implementation in the ICU (Bach & Hetland, 2022; Tirona, 2023). Dubb et al. (2016) and Costa et al. (2017) found that conducting surveys regarding perceived barriers to implementation of EM can help the facility determine the unique barriers they will face and develop strategies to overcome those barriers.

Sixty-two percent of the studies reviewed by Dubb et al. (2016) identified strategies related to overcoming structural barriers. The top three strategies to overcome structural barriers were found to be implementation of protocols, increased staffing, and the purchasing of new equipment. Dirkes and Kozlowski (2019) reported that the use of new mobility beds can be beneficial in implementing an EM protocol by assisting the nurses and ancillary staff in mobilizing patients. In regard to staffing, Escalon et al. (2020) were able to increase the PT staffing from 1.7 to 2.7 in the ICU during EM implementation by pooling the PTs from other

areas of the hospital. The increase in PTs during the protocol implementation enabled more consults to occur, which does not necessarily contribute to implementation success but was seen by Escalon et al. (2020) to be a sign of improved ICU culture and acceptance of the EM protocol.

Summary

The literature review consisted of several topics related to EM in critically ill patients. EM is essential for preventing ICU-AW. Studies found that ICU-AW occurred in approximately 31% of critically ill patients globally and the only modifiable risk factor to address it was mobility. Mobilization in the ICU using EPM protocols has been shown to decrease ICU LOS, decrease time on MV, and lower incidence of mortality. The most successful EPM protocols use BMAT tools, which are nurse-driven and allow the nurse to evaluate the patient's functional status to determine if the patient can be safely mobilized. The literature identified several facilitators and barriers to the implementation of an EPM protocol. Facilitators include providing education to nurses and encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure that EPM protocols are adopted. Barriers were related to inadequate nurse training, staffing shortages and reluctance to move critically ill patients. The strategies used in the EPM protocols are directed at EM of the critically ill patients; however, to be successful, facilities must focus on an interdisciplinary approach, nurse-driven protocols, education, and patient safety screenings. The present project implemented all four identified areas to address EPM in the ICU.

Methods

The purpose of this Nursing Doctoral Project was to implement an EPM protocol in the ICU to decrease ICU -AW by reducing ICU LOS and increasing BMAT scores. This project was implemented using the STAR model as its theoretical framework. The project involved education on the protocol, evaluation of nurse attitudes, and benefits and challenges of the implementation of the EPM protocol, and comparison of the ICU LOS and BMAT scores pre- and post-implementation. The STAR model was used to guide the implementation of this project using the five stages of knowledge transformation: 1. Discovery Research, 2. Evidence Summary, 3. Translation to Guidelines, 4. Practice Integration, and 5. Process, Outcome Evaluation (Stevens, 2022; Figure 1, Appendix A). The objectives for this project were to: (a) conduct a pre-test to assess nursing attitudes towards implementing the EPM protocol and evaluate the ICU LOS and BMAT scores 30 days prior to protocol implementation, (b) educate the nursing staff in the ICU on the EPM protocol, (c) implement the EPM protocol in the ICU (d) conduct a post-test to assess nursing attitudes after implementing the EPM protocol and evaluate the ICU LOS and BMAT scores 30 days post-implementation.

Project Design

The new EPM protocol was introduced to the ICU and implemented into the nurse workflow at the project facility. An EB methodology was used to meet the outlined objectives of this project. The main objective of this project was to decrease the incidence of ICU-AW by reducing ICU LOS and improving the BMAT scores among ICU patients. The PL used Aarons' (2004) Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale (EBPAS©) to collect pre- and post-data on the attitudes and willingness of the nurses towards the use of the EPM protocol, which was collected

along the ICU LOS data and BMAT scores 30 days pre- and post-implementation of the EPM protocol in the ICU.

Setting

This project was conducted in a 36-bed multidisciplinary ICU at a 354-bed acute care hospital in Southern California.

Participants

The sample included all facility employed ICU registered nurses (RNs) from February 2024 to April 2024. Only ICU RNs were included in the study, RNs who do not work in the ICU were excluded. ICU patients were not included in the sample.

Ethical Considerations

An Institutional Review Board (IRB) exemption was obtained from California State University, Los Angeles IRB, as shown in Appendix C. Approval from the project facility was obtained. Refer to Appendix D: Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Project Summary and Appendix E: DNP Project Letter of Support. There was no collection of identifiable information from the participants. All data were anonymous and de-identified. Information and data pertaining to this project are stored in a password-protected computer in a locked office to which the project lead only has access.

Procedures

The STAR Model is the framework that was used to guide this DNP project. The STAR Model's five stages of knowledge transformation were used to implement this project.

Star Point 1: Discovery Research

The first stage was gathering new knowledge through a ROL. The ROL provided information regarding prevention of ICU-AW, tools, and protocols for EPM, barriers and facilitators to EPM, and strategies to implement EPM in acute care settings.

Star Point 2: Evidence Summary

The second stage was synthesis of the information obtained through the ROL to identify the strongest evidence to support the use of the EPM implementation.

Star Point 3: Translation to Guidelines

In the third stage, guidelines for implementing the EPM protocol were developed using the synthesized EBPs. The current charting system requires all ICU patients to be assessed for mobility. However, no specific protocol was established to guide nurses in charting mobility levels or to implement progressive mobility in this facility.

1. A pre-and post-survey was created using Qualtrics©, which included nurse demographics (Figure 3, Appendix F) and included the EBPAS© (Figure 4, Appendix G). The PL developed the nurse demographics questionnaire to include gender, years of experience, certifications, and academic degrees. The EBPAS© assessed nurses' attitudes and willingness to use the EPM protocol.
2. Education materials for the ICU nurses regarding the new EPM protocol were developed to optimize education. A poster board with the protocol was created and placed in the nursing conference room for reference. Badge buddies with the EPM protocol were created and distributed to the nurses. In addition, a turning schedule was created by the unit manager and implemented in the ICU to facilitate the implementation of the EPM protocol.

3. A data collection tool was developed with the help of the EMR analysts for retrieving de-identified data on ICU LOS and BMAT scores both 30 days pre- and post-implementation.

Star Point 4: Practice Integration

The fourth stage of this project involved applying the newly established guidelines into practice and implementing the protocol. This portion of the involved identifying the key stakeholders. The key stakeholders for this project are the ICU director, the ICU Medical Director, ICU Intensivists, ICU Nursing Supervisor, and ICU nurses. For the purpose of this project, CSULA issued an IRB exemption (Appendix C), and written permission was obtained from the project site (Appendix D; Appendix E). The stakeholders were presented with the education materials for approval and then nurses were educated on the EPM protocol. The procedure occurred as follows:

1. Data was collected 30 days prior to EPM protocol implementation on ICU LOS and BMAT scores an anonymous report developed by facility EMR analysts.
2. A pre-implementation online survey, including demographics, was administered to assess the nurses' attitudes toward and willingness to use the EPM protocol (Figure 3, Appendix F; Figure 4, Appendix G). The demographic portion of the survey (Figure 3, Appendix F) was only given to ICU nurses and consisted of questions that identify the nurse's age, gender, ethnicity, years of experience as a nurse, years of experience as an ICU nurse, work status (full-time, part-time, and per diem), specialty certifications, and academic degrees obtained (associate degree, bachelor's degree, master's degree, or Doctorate). The EBPA scale is a tool used to measure the attitudes of participants toward adopting EBP and was used in this project to evaluate the nurse's attitudes toward using the EPM

protocol (Aarons, 2004) (Figure 4, Appendix G). Dr. Gregory Aarons' EBPAS© was used with implied permission.

3. ICU nurses were educated regarding the new EPM protocol over a seven day period.
 - a. Nurses had the opportunity to receive education at the morning or evening huddle.
 - b. Education occurred over a seven day period to ensure all nurses received education and training. A sign in sheet was utilized to ensure all nurses received the training.
4. Implementation of the EPM protocol in the ICU began March 2024. First education and training on the EPM protocol occurred between March 3rd, 2024, to March 9th, 2024, via in person education during morning and night shift huddles over a seven day period in which all ICU nurses were educated. The nurses were instructed on the MOVEN safety criteria for patient mobility and Level 1-4 of progressive mobility (Figure 2, Appendix B). The nurses were instructed to start at Level 1 of mobility for all patients who did not meet all MOVEN safety criteria. Patients who met all MOVEN safety criteria were started at Level 2 and progressed as appropriate. The nurses assessed their patients once a shift for mobility and charted the mobility level on the EMR system in the designated area for BMAT scores.
5. The post-implementation online survey, including demographics, was administered to assess the nurses' attitudes toward and willingness to use the EPM protocol.
6. Data on ICU LOS and BMAT scores was collected 30 days post-EPM protocol implementation through a de-identified report developed by facility EMR analysts.

Star Point 5: Process, Outcome Evaluation

The final stage was the evaluation of the EPM protocol and its effect on ICU LOS and BMAT scores. Data was obtained and examined by the PL and used to evaluate the outcomes of this project.

Data Collection and Storage. The EBPAS© was used to assess the nurses' attitudes towards the implementation of the new EPM protocol both prior to education and post-education. The de-identified data was collected using a secure password-protected database called Qualtrics©. ICU LOS and BMAT scores were obtained using a de-identified and individualized reporting tool on the EMR which is password protected and only accessible by the PL. All collected data was stored on a password protected computer in a locked office which the PL only had access to.

Data Comparison, Analysis, and Evaluation. The PL analyzed demographic data and pre- and post-EBPA scale scores. Independent t-tests were used to compare mean differences between the EBPAS© score pre- and post-intervention. The demographic characteristics of the participants were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including means, frequencies, ranges, and standard deviations, depending on the level of measurement. The PL also evaluated and compared the pre- and post-intervention ICU LOS and BMAT scores. Independent t-test was used to compare mean differences between the ICU LOS and BMAT scores pre- and post-intervention. A .05 criterion for statistical significance was employed for all data analyses. All data was analyzed using SPSS version 28 software.

Results

The initial implementation of the project occurred by retrieving the data on ICU LOS and BMAT scores 30 days prior to education using a de-identified report created by EMR analysts for ICU LOS and BMAT scores. The ICU nurses also took the demographic and EBPAS© survey via Qualtrics© prior to the EPM education. Data was then collected post-implementation on ICU LOS and BMAT scores as well as data from the demographic and EBPAS© survey via Qualtrics©.

Participant Demographics

A total of 49 RNs pre-education and 59 RNs post-education participated in the demographic survey. In both pre- and post- surveys, the majority of the sample was made up of females between the ages of 21-40 with bachelor's degrees who are employed by the facility full-time and have less than two years of ICU experience. Of the nurses who completed the survey, less than 27% had a national nursing certification. Demographic data synthesized from the Qualtrics© survey are displayed in Table 1 below.

Pre and Post EBPAS© Survey

Aarons' EBPAS© scale was created to assess the attitudes toward the acceptance and implementation of EBPs in the real world real-world setting (2004). For the purpose of this project, EBPAS© was used to assess the attitudes toward the implementation of the EPM protocol in the ICU. The EBPAS© scale assesses attitudes toward the application of EBP by breaking down questions into the following four subscales: intuitive Appeal, attitudes toward organizational Requirements, Openness to innovation, and perceived Divergence of research-based innovation (Aarons, 2004). Independent t-test was used to compare EBPAS sub-scores pre- and post-implementation. Among the four subscales (Requirements, Appeal, Openness, and

Divergence), the only statistically significant differences in means for pre- and post-implementation were observed in Subscale 1: Requirements (Mean = 0.5, SD = 1.4), $t(39) = 4.8$, $p = .028$). This indicates an increase in staff acceptance to implement the new practice when it was required. This finding suggests that the EPM protocol's becoming a facility requirement was associated with a statistically significant change during the post-implementation survey. Figure 3 in Appendix I depicts a bar graph illustrating the EBPAS© pre and post mean averages. In Figures 4-7 of Appendix I, the pre- and post-implementation results are displayed independently for each of the 4 EBPAS© subscales (Requirements, Appeal, Openness, and Divergence).

Pre- and Post-ICU LOS and BMAT Scores

For the purpose of this project, de-identified data on ICU LOS and BMAT scores were collected only on ICU admitted patients, however, all patients who were bedded in the ICU regardless of level of care (LOC) or downgrade status received EPM. Data was pulled only on patients with ICU LOC for the period of March 10th, 2024, to April 10th, 2024, using an individualized de-identified report created by EMR analysts for ICU LOS and BMAT scores. Results showed an improvement in ICU LOS from 5.29 days from February 1, 2024 to February 29, 2024, to 3.24 from March 10th, 2024, to April 10th, 2024. ICU LOS average decreased by 1.33 days), and average BMAT scores increased by 0.47 (Appendix J, Figures 8 and 9). Results of the independent t-test did not indicate statistical significance mean differences in ICU LOS and BMAT scores before and after implementation.

Discussion

For the purpose of this project, the PL created and implemented an EPM protocol for ICU patients in a multi-specialty ICU to reduce the incidence of ICU-AW. The EPM protocol was implemented using the 5-star model of knowledge transformation, which was developed to implement new EBP guidelines into practice. De-identified demographic and EBPAS© data was collected through Qualtrics©. ICU LOS and BMAT score data was collected via a specially created reporting tool that provided de-identified data. Demographic data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and all other data was analyzed using SPSS Version 28 software. Data was displayed in tables, pivot charts, and bar graphs.

The results of this quality improvement project aimed to assess the impact of implementing an EPM protocol suggest mixed outcomes. Although the study did not find statistically significant improvements in ICU LOS and BMAT scores, feedback from nurses indicated a perceived improvement in patient well-being. The absence of statistically significant improvement in ICU LOS and BMAT scores could be attributed to several factors. Comparing these findings to previous research, studies have shown varied results regarding the efficacy of EPM protocols. For instance, earlier research has documented significant reductions in ICU LOS and improvements in physical function metrics, suggesting that EPM can be highly effective (Schallom et al., 2020). However, these studies often involved more controlled environments or longer implementation periods, such as the 12 month study done by Schallom et al. (2020), which might account for the discrepancies observed in this project.

Nurse Engagement and Education

The significant finding from the independent t-test for EBPAS© Subscale 1, which suggests that making the EPM protocol a requirement led to increased acceptance and likely

adherence among the staff. This indicates that organizational policies mandating protocol use can significantly influence staff behavior and protocol implementation fidelity, which in turn could lead to more consistent application of the EPM protocol and potentially better outcomes in the future. The significant change in staff behavior as evidenced by the EBPAS© Subscale 1 results aligns with findings from behavior research, which suggests that mandatory policies can enhance protocol adherence (Guha, 2020). This underlines the importance of administrative support and mandatory policies in successful protocol implementation.

Demographics and Experience

The demographic data showing a majority of young, less experienced nurses might also play a role in how new protocols are adopted and implemented. Kelly et al. (2020), found that younger nurses (Generation X & Y) were 2.7 times more likely to access protocols and policies, indicating that enthusiasm and adaptability of younger staff could be advantageous. However, their lack of experience might also mean a need for ongoing education and support to ensure effective protocol implementation.

Limitations

Mobility is important and is essential for the overall well-being of the critically ill patient. Although a new protocol was in place and staff received adequate education, it was difficult to encourage mobilization due to fear. Through discussions with the nurses during huddle and based on survey responses, the common theme was fear of causing harm to a patient who is already very sick. Nurses remained reluctant to mobilize ICU patients despite EPM protocol due to safety concerns. Many patients have multiple lines, tubes, and drains which were a challenge to manage by one nurse in addition to assisting a patient to mobilize due to lack of additional resources on self-determined time constraints. During education huddles on the EPM protocol,

nurses were astonished to learn about the hazards of immobility and were eager to make a change but many still did not mobilize majority of the patients past mobility Level 1.

Results of the implementation of the EPM protocol lacked a statistically significant improvement in BMAT scores which could be non-adherence to the EPM tool or it could be related to incorrect charting on the EMR. It was difficult to determine if the patients were being mobilized and the charting was not reflecting their true mobility level or if the patients were truly only mobilized to Level 1.

The marginal decrease in ICU LOS and a slight increase in BMAT scores suggest that while there may be trends toward improvement, the study may have been underpowered to detect statistically significant differences. This highlights a potential need for larger sample sizes or extended study durations to capture meaningful data. Furthermore, the initial stages of implementing a new clinical protocol often involve a learning curve and variability in adherence, which might have diluted the potential impact of the EPM protocol.

Recommendations

In order to reduce the incidence of ICU-AW there needs to be an improvement in ICU LOS and patient mobility scores (BMAT). According to post-survey results, the nurses felt there were challenges in EPM protocol implementation due to insufficient resources, time constraints, and lack of training. In order to promote success in the implementation of a new EPM protocol in the ICU continued training on the use and safety of the EPM tool is essential. The use of enhanced training resources such as tip sheets and badge buddies can optimize staff engagement and understanding when learning about a new protocol, which in turn will lead to a greater likelihood that a new protocol is used (Labrague, 2024). For this project, badge buddies and tip sheets were created and made available to all nurses. In regards to time constraints, a turning

schedule was developed, and turning buddies/teams were created to assist the nurses in mobility during their shifts. Physical therapists can also be a resource for added mobility and as a partner in care, they can help the patients work on mobility goals during physical therapy sessions. Staff should also be encouraged to use Safe Patient Handling and Mobility (SPHM) technologies to safely mobilize patients and prevent injuries (U.S. Department of Veteran Affairs, 2024).

Another recommendation for the future success of EPM protocols in the ICU is to introduce daily audits/mobility rounds to ensure every patient receives EPM. To promote overall better patient outcomes EPM should also be considered for expansion throughout the hospital as a mobility initiative to ensure all patients in all departments participate in early progressive mobility. Lastly, to have a successful implementation of a new protocol such as EPM, it is essential to maintain staff commitment, interprofessional involvement, and organizational support for EPM protocol implementation.

Conclusion

Overall, while the statistical data did not demonstrate significant improvements, the positive qualitative feedback and changes in staff behavior towards the EPM protocol are promising. These findings suggest that with continued training, increased sample sizes for further studies, and perhaps modifications to the protocol or its metrics, there is potential for this intervention to show more pronounced benefits in future assessments. The study underscores the complexity of integrating new health interventions in ICU settings and highlights the importance of considering both qualitative feedback and quantitative data when evaluating the impact of such implementations.

References

- Aarons, G. A. (2004). Mental health provider attitudes toward adoption of evidence-based practice: The evidence-based practice attitude scale (EBPAS). *Mental Health Services Research, 6*(2), 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.1023/b:mhsr.0000024351.12294.65>
- Alamri, M. S., Waked, I. S., Amin, F. M., Al-Quliti, K. W., & Manzar, M. D. (2019). Effectiveness of an early mobility protocol for stroke patients in Intensive Care Unit. *Neurosciences (Riyadh, Saudi Arabia), 24*(2), 81–88. <https://doi.org/10.17712/nsj.2019.2.20180004>
- American Association of Critical Care Nurses (AACN). (2013). Executing evidence based progressive mobility in the ICU. <https://www.scribd.com/document/464723380/httpswww-aacn-orgdocsEventPlanningWB0007Mobility-Protocol-szh4mr5a-pdf-pdf>
- Amundadóttir, O. R., Jónasdóttir, R. J., Sigvaldason, K., Gunnsteinsdóttir, E., Haraldsdóttir, B., Sveinsson, T., Sigurdsson, G. H., & Dean, E. (2021). Effects of intensive upright mobilization on outcomes of mechanically ventilated patients in the intensive care unit: a randomized controlled trial with 12-months follow-up. *European Journal of Physiotherapy, 23*(2), 68–78.
- Bach, C., & Hetland, B. (2022). A step forward for intensive care unit patients: Early mobility interventions and associated outcome measures. *Critical Care Nurse, 42*(6), 13–24. <https://doi.org/10.4037/ccn2022459>
- Bonis, S., Taft, L., & Wendler, MC. (2007). Strategies to promote success on the NCLEX-RN: an evidence-based approach using the ACE Star Model of Knowledge Transformation. *Nursing Education Perspectives (National League for Nursing), 28*(2), 82–87.

- Boynton, T., Kumpar, D., & VanGilder, C. (2020). *The bedside mobility assessment tool 2.0*.
<https://www.myamericannurse.com/the-bedside-mobility-assessment-tool-2-0/>
- Garcia, F. (2020). Prioritizing acute care education in renal transplant recipients: An evidenced based approach with the ACE STAR model of knowledge transformation. University of Houston Libraries. <https://uh-ir.tdl.org/handle/10657/7077>
- Dirkes, S. M., & Kozlowski, C. (2019). Early mobility in the intensive care unit: Evidence, barriers, and future directions. *Critical Care Nurse*, 39(3), 33–42.
<https://doi.org/10.4037/ccn2019654>
- Dubb, R., Nydahl, P., Hermes, C., Schwabbauer, N., Toonstra, A., Parker, A. M., Kaltwasser, A., & Needham, D. M. (2016). Barriers and strategies for early mobilization of patients in intensive care units. *Annals of the American Thoracic Society*, 13(5), 724–730.
<https://doi.org/10.1513/AnnalsATS.201509-586CME>
- Escalon, M. X., Lichtenstein, A. H., Posner, E., Spielman, L., Delgado, A., & Kolakowsky-Hayner, S. A. (2020). The effects of early mobilization on patients requiring extended mechanical ventilation across multiple ICUs. *Critical Care Explorations*, 2(6), e0119.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/CCE.0000000000000119>
- Falkenstein, B. A., Skalkowski, C. K., Lodise, K. D., Moore, M., Olkowski, B. F., & Rojavin, Y. (2020). The economic and clinical impact of an early mobility program in the trauma intensive care unit: A quality improvement project. *Journal of Trauma Nursing*, 27(1), 29–36. <https://doi-org./10.1097/JTN.0000000000000479>
- Guha, P. (2020). Why comply with an unenforced policy? The case of mandated corporate social responsibility in India. *Policy Design and Practice*, 3(1), 58–72.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2020.1726592>

- Kelly, U., Edwards, G., & Shapiro, S. E. (2020). Nursing policies and protocols. *Journal of Nursing Care Quality*, 36(3), 217–222. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ncq.0000000000000532>
- Labrague, L. J. (2024). Nurses' adherence to patient safety protocols and its relationship with adverse patient events. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, 56(2), 282–290.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/jnu.12942>
- Maggio, L. A., Sewell, J. L., & Artino, A. R. (2016). The literature review: A foundation for high-quality medical education research. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 8(3), 297–303. <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-D-16-00175.1>
- Nursing Bird. (2022). The ACE Star Model of Knowledge Transformation.
<https://nursingbird.com/the-ace-star-model-of-knowledge-transformation/>
- Sarfati, Moore, A., Pilorge, C., Amaru, P., Mendialdua, P., Rodet, E., Stéphan, F., & Rezaiguia-Delclaux, S. (2018). Efficacy of early passive tilting in minimizing ICU-acquired weakness: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Critical Care*, 46, 37–43.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrc.2018.03.031>
- Schallom, M., Tymkew, H., Vyers, K., Prentice, D., Sona, C., Norris, T., & Arroyo, C. (2020). Implementation of an interdisciplinary AACN Early Mobility Protocol. *Critical Care Nurse*, 40(4), e7–e17. <https://doi.org/10.4037/ccn2020632>
- Stevens, K. (2013). The impact of evidence-based practice in nursing and the next big ideas. *The Online Journal of Issues in Nursing*, 18(2).
<https://doi.org/10.3912/OJIN.Vol18No02Man04>
- Stevens, K. (2022). *STAR model*. <https://uthscsa.edu/nursing/research/resources-scholarly-support/star-model>

Tirona, K. (2023). Just keep MOVEN: An evidenced based approach to improving outcomes in patients receiving mechanical ventilation. *Critical Care Nurse*, 43(1), 75-78.

<https://doi.org/10.4037/ccn2023754>

Turner, R., Agarwal, N., Agarwal, S., & Best, L. (2020). Bringing Life to a systemwide early mobility clinical practice: Part 1. *International Journal of Safe Patient Handling & Mobility (SPHM)*, 10(4), 126–132.

U.S. Department of Veteran Affairs. (2024). *Safe patient handling and mobility*. Retrieved from

<https://www.publichealth.va.gov/employeehealth/patient-handling/>

Appendix A

Figure 1: Stevens STAR Model of Knowledge Transformation

Note: Used with expressed permission 2015

Appendix B

Figure 2: AACN's Early Progressive Mobility Protocol

Early Progressive Mobility Protocol

STEP 1: Screen for Safety

Evaluate daily

M Myocardial Stability

- No active cardiac ischemia within past 12-24 h
- No dysrhythmia requiring new antidysrhythmic agent within past 12-24 h

O Oxygenation Stability

- $FiO_2 < 0.85$ on mechanical ventilation
- PEEP < 15 cm H_2O
- No unsecured airway

V Vasopressor Use

- No new or increase of any vasopressor for 2 h

E Engages to Voice

- Responds to verbal stimulation
- RASS $< +3$, or SAS < 6

N Neuro Stability

- ICP < 15
- No acute or uncontrolled intracranial event

Does not meet criteria = Start at Level 1 and evaluate in 12 h

Meets all criteria = Start at Level 2 and progress

STEP 2: Implement Progressive Mobility

Goal: Clinical stability and able to move arm against gravity

- Passive ROM 3 times a day
- Turn every 2 h
- Active-resistance PT
- Sitting position 20 min 3 times a day

Goal: Sitting upright and able to move leg against gravity

- Passive ROM 3 times a day
- Turn every 2 h
- Active-resistance PT
- Sitting position 20 min 3 times a day
- Sitting on edge of bed

Goal: Increased strength and stands with minimal to moderate assistance

- Turn every 2 h
- Active-resistance PT
- Sitting position 20 min 3 times a day
- Sitting on edge of bed
- Active transfer to chair ≥ 20 min 2 times a day

Goal: Strength and distance walk

- Self- or assisted turn every 2 h
- Active-resistance PT
- Active transfer to chair ≥ 20 min 3 times a day
- Ambulation (marching in place, walking in halls)

Appendix C

IRB Letter of Exemption

Office Memorandum

DATE: February 26, 2024

TO: Ayman Tailakh, PhD

FROM: Claire Riner

PROJECT TITLE: [2100526-1] Implementation of an Early Mobility Protocol in the Intensive Care Unit

REFERENCE #: 23-96X

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS

DECISION DATE: February 26, 2024

REVIEW CATEGORY: Exemption category # 2(i), 2(ii), & 4(ii)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Claire Riner. **It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.**

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

Appendix D

Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Project Summary

Project Title:

Implementation of an Early Progressive Mobility Protocol in the Intensive Care Unit

Lead Student:

Helene Mendez, MSN, RN, AGACNP-BC, CCRN

Mentor:

Anna Carchi, DNP, ACNP, CNS at St. Francis Medical Center

Faculty Team Leader:

Ayman Tailakh, Ph.D., RN

Faculty Team Member:

Raymond Gantioque, DNP, RNFA, ACNP-BC

About the Project:

We're introducing and implementing an Early Progressive Mobility Protocol (EPM) in the ICU/CCU at SFMC for research purposes. This involves:

- **Surveys:** A before-and-after survey to understand nurses' views on the new protocol.
- **Training:** Educating ICU nurses on benefits and how to use and document EPM during huddles.
- **Implementation:** Including EPM in the ICU workflow with help from the ICU director.
- **Data Collection:** Comparing data from 30 days before and after the EPM introduction, focusing on ICU stay lengths and BMAT scores. All data will be aggregated, deidentified, anonymous, and collected from October to December 2023.
- **Subjects:** Participants must be 18 years and older and may skip any question they do not wish to answer.

Privacy Matters:

- **Anonymity:** No names or identifying details will be attached to the data or the project's published findings.
- **Security:** All collected information will be securely stored and used only for this project.

Oversight:

- An Institutional Review Board (IRB) approval is obtained from California State University.

Risks and Gains:

- **Safety:** There's minimal risk involved as we won't interact directly with patients or access personal information.
- **Focus:** The aim is to understand the impact of the new EPM protocol, not individual performance.

Questions?

Reach out to the lead investigator, Ayman Tailakh at Ayman.Tailak@calstatela.edu.

Thank you for participating and contributing to this vital initiative to enhance patient care in the ICU!

IRB STATEMENT

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

Appendix E

Letter of Support

Subject: Organizational Support for Quality Improvement Project - Implementation of an Early Progressive Mobility Protocol in the Intensive Care Unit

To Whom it May Concern:

We are pleased to confirm our full support for Helene Mendez, MSN, RN, AGACNP-BC in the execution of her Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project titled "Implementation of an Early Progressive Mobility Protocol in the Intensive Care Unit". This project aims to develop and implement an Early Progressive Mobility screening tool and protocol in the ICU in order to improve patient mobility and reduce the incidence of ICU Acquired Weakness (ICU-AW).

As an organization, we are committed to providing the necessary support and resources to facilitate the successful implementation of this project within St. Francis Medical Center. We will offer on-site guidance and ensure the provision of appropriate resources as required. Additionally, we will assist in obtaining any necessary approvals for data collection and storage in accordance with our local site requirements and institutional policies and procedures.

We are pleased to designate Anna Carchi, DNP, ACNP, CNS as the site organizational sponsor for this project. Dr. Carchi's extensive experience and qualifications make her well-suited for this role, and she will provide guidance and oversight throughout the project.

To safeguard patient privacy and comply with regulatory requirements, all data used for this project will undergo a rigorous de-identification process. Personally identifiable information (PII) and protected health information (PHI) will be removed before being made accessible to the project lead.

We firmly believe that this quality improvement initiative has the potential to significantly reduce the incidence of ICU-AW, enhance the performance of our standard patient mobility process, and improve overall outcomes for critically ill patients in the ICU. We are confident in Ms. Mendez's dedication and expertise in leading this project, and we look forward to witnessing the positive impact it will have on our organization and the broader medical community.

Should you require any further information or have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me at Paryus.Patel@Primehealthcare.com. Thank you for your attention to this matter.

Sincerely,

Paryus Patel, M.D.
Corporate CMO | PrimeHealthcare CMO | Centinela Hospital Medical Center
 555 East Hardy Street | Inglewood, CA 90301
 Ph: 310.680.8095 | Fax: 310.677.0535
 Paryus.Patel@Primehealthcare.com

Appendix F

Demographic Survey

Demographic Survey

1. What is your age?

- 21-30
- 31-40
- 41-50
- 51-60
- 61-70
- 71-80
- Prefer to not respond

2. Which Gender do you identify as?

- Male
- Female
- Transgender
- Other: _____
- Prefer to not respond

3. Which Ethnicity do you identify as?

- Caucasian
- African American
- Hispanic or Latino
- Asian or Pacific Islander
- Indian
- Other: _____
- Prefer to not respond

4. How many years of nursing experience do you have?

- <2 years
- 2-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 10 + years

5. How many years of ICU experience do you have?

- <2 years
- 2-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 10 + years

6. Are you:

- Full-time
- Part-time
- Per diem

7. Do you currently hold a specialty board certification? (i.e. Certified Emergency Nurse (CEN), Stroke Certified Registered Nurse (SCRN), Critical Care Registered Nurse (CCRN))

- Yes: Please specify: _____
- No

8. What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? If currently enrolled, check highest degree received.

- Trade/technical/vocational training
- Associate degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Doctorate degree

Appendix G

Evidence-Based Practice Attitude

EBPAS[®] Gregory A. Aarons, Ph.D.

Reference:

Aarons, G. A. (2004). Mental health provider attitudes toward adoption of evidence-based practice: The Evidence-Based Practice Attitude Scale. *Mental Health Services Research, 6*(2), 61-74.

The following questions ask about your feelings about using the Early Progressive Mobility Protocol.

Fill in the circle indicating the extent to which you agree with each item using the following scale:

	0	1	2	3	4
	Not at All	To a Slight Extent	To a Moderate Extent	To a Great Extent	To a Very Great Extent
	0	1	2	3	4
1. I like to use new types of therapy/interventions to help my clients.....	<input type="radio"/>				
2. I am willing to try new types of therapy/interventions even if I have to follow a treatment manual.....	<input type="radio"/>				
3. I know better than academic researchers how to care for my clients.....	<input type="radio"/>				
4. I am willing to use new and different types of therapy/interventions developed by researchers.....	<input type="radio"/>				
5. Research based treatments/interventions are not clinically useful.....	<input type="radio"/>				
6. Clinical experience is more important than using manualized therapy/treatment.....	<input type="radio"/>				
7. I would not use manualized therapy/interventions.....	<input type="radio"/>				
8. I would try a new therapy/intervention even if it were very different from what I am used to doing.....	<input type="radio"/>				
For questions 9-15: If you received training in a therapy or intervention that was new to you, how likely would you be to adopt it if:					
9. it was intuitively appealing?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
10. it "made sense" to you?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
11. it was required by your supervisor?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
12. it was required by your agency?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
13. it was required by your state?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
14. it was being used by colleagues who were happy with it?.....	<input type="radio"/>				
15. you felt you had enough training to use it correctly?.....	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix H

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Measure	Pre-Survey		Post-Survey	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Gender				
Male	14	28.6%	16	27.1%
Female	33	67.3%	42	71.2%
Prefer not to respond	2	4.1%	1	1.7%
Ethnicity				
White	5	10.2%	4	6.8%
Black	9	18.4%	14	23.7%
Asian	14	28.6%	20	33.9%
Native Hawaiian	2	4.1%	1	1.7%
Hispanic	15	30.6%	16	27.1%
Other	4	8.2%	4	6.8%
Age				
21-30	16	32.7%	21	35.6%
31-40	17	34.7%	14	23.7%
41-50	4	8.2%	5	8.5%
51-60	8	16.3%	13	22.0%
61-70	2	4.1%	4	6.8%
71-80	0	0%	1	1.7%
Prefer not to respond	2	4.1%	1	1.7%
Employment status				
Full-time	44	89.8 %	55	93.2%
Part-time	4	8.16%	2	3.4%
Per diem	1	2.04%	2	3.4%

Measure	Pre-Survey		Post-Survey	
	Frequency	Percentage	Measure	Frequency
Level of Education				
Master's degree	5	10.2%	7	11.9%
Bachelor's degree	36	73.5%	44	74.6%
Associate degree	8	16.3%	8	13.6%
Years of Nursing Experience				
<2 years	17	34.7%	18	30.5%
2-5 years	5	10.2%	13	22.0%
6-10 years	12	24.5%	8	13.6%
10 + years	15	30.6%	20	33.9%
Years of ICU Experience				
<2 years	23	46.9%	34	57.6%
2-5 years	11	22.4%	10	16.9%
6-10 years	7	14.3%	4	6.8%
10 + years	8	16.3%	10	16.9%
Specialty Board Certification				
Yes	13	26.5%	13	22.0%
No	34	69.4%	44	74.6%

Note. Table depicts percentage of project participants for each descriptive measure.

Appendix I

EBPAS: Pre- and Post- Mean Averages

Appendix I

Figure 4: EBPAS©: Subscale 1- Requirements

Appendix I

Figure 5: EBPAS©: Subscale 2- Appeal

Appendix I

Figure 6: EBPAS©: Subscale 3 -Openness

Appendix I

Figure 7: EBPAS©: Subscale 4 -Divergence

Appendix J

Figure 8: Average ICU LOS

Appendix J

Figure 9: Average ICU LOS